

Dyes Derived from Substituted Phthalic Acids. Part IV. 3,4-Dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic Acid

S. D. Loiwal and N. G. Jain

3,4-Dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic acid, prepared in the form of its anhydride, has been used for the preparation of some phthalein and rhodamine types of compounds. The resorcinol compound of the acid has also been brominated and acetylated.

3-Methyl-2-ethyl-1,3-pentadiene (I), obtained from methylethyl ketone has been condensed with maleic anhydride to yield 3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (II)¹. The anhydride (II) has been condensed with resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol, *m*-diethylaminophenol, phenol, and *o*-cresol. The resorcinol compound has been brominated and acetylated. The dyes obtained have been studied spectrophotometrically and compared with the dyes obtained from phthalic acid.

The phthaleins and rhodamines obtained are of the following two types:

- III : $\text{R}^1=\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{OH}$.
 IV : $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{OH}$.
 V : $\text{R}^1=\text{R}^3=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{H}$.
 VI : $\text{R}^1=\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{N}(\text{Et})_2$.
 VII : $\text{R}^1=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{Br}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{OH}$.
 VIII: $\text{R}^1=\text{R}^2=\text{R}^4=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{OCOMe}$.

- IX : $\text{R}^1=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}^2=\text{H}$.
 X : $\text{R}^1=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl ethyl ketone was first converted into 3,4-dimethyl-3,4-hexane diol¹ (b.p. 98-106°/6mm). The diol was then dehydrated with 20% H₂SO₄ to 3-methyl-2-ethyl-1,3-pentadiene (I) (b. p. 136°/760mm)¹. The diene (I) on condensation with maleic anhydride afforded 3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (II). The anhydride (II) was crystallised from light petroleum (40-60°), m.p. 104°. The phthaleins and rhodamines described below were then prepared, using this anhydride (II) by methods described earlier².

Resorcinol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (III) was obtained by condensation of a mixture of anhydride (II) (2.0 g.) and resorcinol (2.2 g.) at 160° for 3 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3 drops).

Orcinol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IV) was similarly obtained from a mixture of anhydride (II) (2.0 g.) and orcinol (2.76 g.) by heating at 130-40° for 4 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3 drops).

Phloroglucinol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (V) was prepared by heating a mixture of anhydride (II) (2 g.) and phloroglucinol (2.84 g.) at 180-200° for 3 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 4 drops).

m-Diethylaminophenol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VI) was obtained similarly as above by condensation of a mixture of anhydride (II) (2 g.) and *m*-diethylaminophenol (3.3 g.) at 140°.

Tetrabromoresorcinol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VII) was obtained from compound (III) by bromination³.

Resorcinol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein diacetate (VIII) was obtained by acetylating compound (III).

Phenol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IX) was obtained by heating a mixture of anhydride (II) (2 g.) and phenol (5 g.) at 110-15° for 12 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 drops). The excess of phenol was removed by steam distillation.

o-Cresol-3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (X) was similarly obtained from anhydride (II) (2 g.) and *o*-cresol (5 g.) by heating at 115-20° for 13 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 drops).

The characteristic properties and the analytical data of the above compounds are recorded in Table I.

The absorption maxima of the compounds thus prepared were determined as usual², using "Hilger Uvispek" spectrophotometer. The absorptions were of similar nature in the two systems (dyes from 3,4-dimethyl-5-ethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic acid and the dyes from phthalic acid).

2. Loewel and Jain, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 251, 385.

3. Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1878, 183, 3.

TABLE I

Compound No.	M.P.*	C o l o u r o f			Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
		Crystals.	EtOH soln.	EtOH (alk.) soln.			
III	185°	Reddish brown	Orange-yellow	†Pink	$C_{22}H_{24}O_5$	C : 73.20% H : 6.15	73.47% 6.12
IV	155°	Brown	Yellow	†Light pink	$C_{26}H_{28}O_5$	C : 74.10 H : 6.70	74.29 6.66
V	> 300°	Red	Do	Orange	$C_{24}H_{24}O_7$	C : 67.70 H : 5.68	67.92 5.66
VI	165°	Dark pink	Pink	**Intense pink	$C_{32}H_{44}O_5N_2$	C : 76.20 H : 8.40 N : 5.56	76.47 8.37 5.56
VII	> 300°	Dark red	Blood-red	Intense red	$C_{24}H_{20}O_5Br_4$	Br : 45.12	45.20
VIII	120°	Brown	Yellow	Yellow	$C_{28}H_{28}O_7$	C : 70.40 H : 6.90	70.59 5.88
IX	140°	Light brown	Do	Light pink	$C_{24}H_{26}O_4$	C : 76.02 H : 6.90	76.19 6.87
X	165°	Do	Yellowish brown	Dark pink	$C_{26}H_{30}O_4$	C : 76.74 H : 7.42	76.84 7.39

*With decomposition.

**With one drop of 5N-HCl.

†With green fluorescence.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. S. M. Mitra, Principal and to Dr. R. D. Gupta, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Birla College, Pilani, for providing necessary facilities. One of the authors (N. C. Jain) also expresses his gratitude to the Government of India for granting him a research fellowship.